

NDAC/LO/137
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Investigation of 1st sample suppression/inclusion

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INTRODUCTION

In a previous note (NDAC/LO136, 1990 Aug 30) I derived analytically the expected size of the (supposedly) random errors introduced by retaining, in the IDT data analysis, the first sample after repositioning the IFOV to a new star. It was found that the rms phase error of the first harmonic introduced by the corrupted sample varies between 0.34 mas for bright stars and 0.13 mas for faint stars. On the other hand I found that the expected rms reduction of the photon noise, due to the inclusion of that sample, would be less than 0.3 mas for stars brighter than 4th magnitude, increasing to 2 mas around magnitude 9, and 3--4 mas for the faintest stars. Thus the photonstatistical advantage of retaining the first sample would outweigh the noise contribution due to the corruption of the sample for all stars fainter than approximately $H_p = 5$.

This conclusion relies strongly on the assumption that the corrupted sample does not in any way bias the results, at least on the great-circle (abscissa) level. On theoretical grounds there is no reason to expect such a bias, provided that the modulation phase of the first sample is evenly distributed over all angles. This would seem to be guaranteed by the (at least nominal) incommensurability of the IFOV piloting with the modulation period. However, a direct numerical comparison was required to test this assumption, and that is what this report is concerned with.

ABSCISSA DATA

The great-circle comparison set #1 has been carried through the IDT data analysis and great-circle reduction in two variants, one with the first sample suppressed (the current baseline), and one in which the sample was retained at all magnitudes. Only the geometric mode of great-circle reduction was used. Results of the great-circle reductions were summarized by C Petersen (e-mail of Nov 9), but without drawing any conclusion from the data. Following Petersen I will refer to the two data sets as WOUT (without the first sample) and WITH (including the first sample).

The normalized mean error obtained in the great-circle reductions was 1.050 (WOUT) and 1.051 (WITH), respectively. The increase, although perhaps not significant, could indicate the presence of additional noise in the WITH-data, which is not accounted for by the formal standard deviations of the grid coordinates. It is tempting to interpret this as due to the corrupted first sample.

The following Table 1 contains data taken directly from Petersen's report (except the last row, 'All', which I have computed). Note that the abscissa standard deviations given by Petersen are obtained as the formal standard errors, from the inverse normal equations matrix, multiplied by the normalized mean error. The factor 1.050 (or 1.051) is thus already included in the data.

Table 1. Abscissa results from two sets with and without the first IDT sample after IFOV repositioning.

H-mag	N	Average st.d.		WITH - WOUT	
		WOUT	WITH	Average	Rms
3	2	2.097	2.064	0.163	0.505
4	8	2.337	2.297	-0.272	0.642
5	19	2.391	2.350	-0.166	0.568
6	39	2.555	2.511	0.143	0.590
7	158	2.730	2.680	-0.019	0.564
8	375	3.263	3.204	0.045	0.706
9	612	3.910	3.849	0.045	0.770
10	267	5.027	4.956	-0.028	0.859
11	83	6.463	6.394	-0.143	1.406
12	18	10.946	10.842	-1.242	2.895
13	3	9.615	9.605	0.025	1.100
All	1584	3.990	3.929	0.000	0.800

Notes: All values in mas. H-mag = 3 means H-magnitude in the interval 2.5 to 3.5.

ANALYSIS

Let us start by examining the numbers in the last two columns, to see whether they might indicate some unexpected quality of the abscissa differences.

The circumstance that the global average abscissa difference is exactly zero ($\langle \text{WITH} - \text{WOUT} \rangle = 0$ for the whole set) is of course due to the comparison method, which allows an arbitrary zero-point shift of the abscissae. Looking at the mean difference of each magnitude class, there is no obvious trend. Moreover, taking into account the rms differences and the number of abscissae at each magnitude, none of the averages is significantly different from zero. The sum of squared normalized averages is 14.0, with 10 d.o.f., indicating that the data are well consistent with the hypothesis that the true average equals zero at all magnitudes.

Turning now to the last column, I assume that the rms abscissa difference is made up of two independent contributions. One derives from the photon noise of the first sample, which is clearly independent of the photon noise of the second and following samples. Therefore, this contribution can be computed as the difference between the abscissa variances in WOUT and WITH. For instance, for $H_p = 3$, we have

$$\text{sqrt}(2.097**2 - (2.064*1.050/1.051)**2) = 0.38 \text{ mas}$$

where the factor 1.050/1.051 was applied to the standard deviation in WITH in order to make it comparable with WOUT. This gives the second column (e1) in Table 2.

The second noise component, which is not due to photon noise, is obtained by subtracting e1 quadratically from the rms differences in Table 1. This gives us the numbers in the column marked e2 in Table 2. Apart from the large fluctuations at magnitude 10 and fainter, which may be accidental, this noise component is surprisingly constant at about 0.35 mas. In the absence of any other known noise contribution (different in the two sets) we must

attribute it to the corruptness of the first sample.

Table 2. See text for explanation.

H-mag	e1	e2	St.d. WITH	WOUT	p
3	0.38	0.33	2.092	2.097	-0.2 %
4	0.44	0.47	2.321	2.337	-0.6
5	0.45	0.35	2.374	2.391	-0.7
6	0.48	0.34	2.533	2.555	-0.9
7	0.53	0.19	2.700	2.730	-1.1
8	0.63	0.32	3.220	3.263	-1.3
9	0.71	0.30	3.861	3.910	-1.2
10	0.87	--	4.964	5.027	-1.3
11	0.98	1.01	6.397	6.463	-1.0
12	1.58	2.4	10.837	10.946	-1.0
13	0.61	0.92	9.602	9.615	-0.1
All	0.72	0.35	3.942	3.990	-1.2 %

An rms contribution of 0.35 mas on the abscissae from the corrupted sample is larger than expected. In NDAC/LO/136 an rms contribution of about 0.3 mas ON THE GRID COORDINATES was derived from an analytical model. When propagated through the great-circle reduction, involving an averaging over a few tens of frames for each star, the noise on the abscissae should have been on the 0.1 mas level. There is obviously something odd going on here. Possibly 0.35 mas should merely be considered an empirical upper limit to the abscissa noise due to the corrupted sample.

Adopting the figure 0.35 mas for the non-photon-noise contribution, we can compute the 'real' abscissa standard deviations for the WITH set shown in the 4th column of Table 2. They were calculated as in the following example for $H_p = 3$:

$$\text{sqrt}((2.064*1.050/1.051)**2 + 0.35**2) = 2.092$$

The 5th column contains the standard deviations for the WOUT set (from Table 1), and the last column shows the percentage change in standard error from WOUT to WITH.

CONCLUSIONS

From a simple analysis of abscissa differences with and without the first sample there is no evidence for biases, e.g. as a function of magnitude. The rms abscissa differences indicate that the corrupted first sample contributes about 0.35 mas rms to the abscissae. In the geometric solution, this is more than compensated by the reduced photon noise at all magnitudes (3 to 13). Taking into account both factors we find that the total rms abscissa error is reduced by about 1 % if the first sample is retained; this holds for the magnitude range 6 to 12.

It is not understood why the noise contribution is as large as 0.35 mas; on theoretical grounds a value around 0.1 mas was expected. This is not very satisfactory.

The present study does not preclude that biases of a more peculiar nature could exist, so that for instance a small fraction of the objects are significantly affected. It is also noted that the possible

gain in retaining the first sample is small compared with many other effects under investigation, such as abscissa differences between FAST and NDAC.

In view of all this, I propose that the present baseline is continued, namely that the first sample is always suppressed.